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NATIONAL LEADER HEYDAR ALIYEV AND MUSICAL CULTURE OF AZERBAIJAN

Abstract. The article examines National Leader Heydar Aliyev's deep thoughts about musical culture of Azerbaijan, prominent cultural figures and the great state projects he implemented. There was no boundary between different spheres of public life for an outstanding political leader with brilliant innate talent. He addressed every issue he touched upon as a skilled expert, and proved that he had high erudition, deep knowledge and rich life experience in that field.

H. Aliyev attached special importance to the problem of the personality's role in history, appreciated various musical figures and expressed valuable opinions. History and modernity, traditions and historical development are presented as complementary and interconnected categories in the theoretical concept formed in the Great leader's rich ideas about music, various speeches and reports.

Key words: Heydar Aliyev, musical culture, composers, musical figures, national traditions.

Introduction. National leader of Azerbaijan Heydar Aliyev is among the phenomenal personalities in terms of his talent, innate and moral qualities. There were no boundaries between different areas of social life for him. Heydar Aliyev, a prominent statesman, a skilled politician and a wise man, acted as connoisseur and expert of the subject, specialty, or field he spoke of. Heydar Aliyev, who demonstrated high knowledge as a wonderful writer at a literary meeting, an inspired art critic at a cultural event, a master politician and economist in political life, went into the

essence of every topic he talked about, and proved each time that he had high erudition, deep knowledge and rich life experience. His ability to delve into every problem, know it deeply, feel, analyze and summarize it regardless of the field, manifested itself in a brighter and more complete way when the outstanding statesman came to power for the second time in 1993. This was due to the fact that Azerbaijan made a step on the path to independence in the new era, as well as owing to wisdom, accumulation of rich life and political experience of Heydar Aliyev and of course, his deep love for and loyalty to his people. His views about literature and art, about creative intellectuals and especially about big politics, which have received the status of aphorisms due to their essence and generalizing force, confirm the above mentioned.

The interpretation of the main material. Heydar Aliyev, who did a lot for the development of every field of cultural policy, treated literary and cultural figures with special attention and care. He attached special importance to the problem of the role of personality in history in his speeches, which is one of the actual problems of social sciences, and expressed valuable views about various cultural and academic figures. “It is necessary to raise the respect for intellectuals, cultural figures, scientists in the society. Because the nation is always known for its intellectuals, its culture, its science”. “Prominent personalities demonstrate intelligence, science, culture, and spirituality of our people to the world” [7, s.124] – said H. Aliyev, who highly appreciated the great historical work and service performed by the personalities. His views on culture prove once again that Heydar Aliyev had comprehensive knowledge and rich information. As he said, “the nation is recognized and respected and stands out among nations of the world for its many characteristics. The highest and greatest of these characteristics is culture. A nation with a high culture will always move forward, always create, always develop” [6].

Heydar Aliyev, as a person who understood and felt music deeply, expressed theoretical ideas about this form of art. This stemmed from his talent to penetrate the deep layers of all kinds of creativity. “Each work of art has a positive effect on people... – it has a great influence on the formation of their character, development and increase of their cultural level. But the effect shown through a musical work is higher than the effect of all other works” [9]. With these words, H. Aliyev, as a listener, touched on the impact of music on the masses, the theoretical problem of musical

and musical-aesthetic orientation, and justified his opinion by explaining: “If we take into account that the majority of our people were illiterate, could not read and there were very few books, there were no cinema, television and other means at the beginning of our century, imagine how great was the contribution of Uzeyir Hajibeyov to the spiritual and cultural development of our nation who conveyed the words of Muhammad Fuzuli through his opera, the ideas through “Arshin Mal Alan” (“The Cloth Peddler”), “O olmasin, bu olsun” (“If Not That One, Then This One”) and other operettas” [9]. Here, Heydar Aliyev explained the social importance of Uzeyir Hajibeyli’s art. Heydar Aliyev, who valued highly the music of our great composer Muslim Magomayev’s opera “Shah Ismail” as a work of art, also paid special attention to the historical and political role of this work: “The great importance of the opera “Shah Ismail” is not limited only to that of a work of art. Muslim Magomayev addressed this theme not as a composer and art worker, but as a person who knew well the history of Azerbaijan. The fact that he wrote such a beautiful opera addressing this topic is of great importance for art, and also has great historical and political significance” [2]. This value given to the opera is the value of a sensitive musician, a knowledgeable historian, a great political figure and a patriot. So, in his opinion, a musical work, like any work of art, should be perfect not only in form, but also in content, and should serve the society. H. Aliyev also spoke about the unity of the form and content of the work in other speeches: “Uzeyir Hajibeyov did not aim to delight people with beautiful music, to make them laugh and cheer up with the characters of his works, but pursued other goals in the operettas “Arshin Mal Alan” (“The Cloth Peddler”), “O olmasin, bu olsun” (“If Not That One, Then This One). His purpose was to criticize and expose through music the negative aspects in the life of our people – inertia, ignorance, individual customs that hold our people back, open their eyes of the people, develop them and raise the culture and spirituality of the people. Undoubtedly, this reaches every person more quickly through a musical work” [9]. The speaker appreciated in his speech the beautiful music of the genius composer’s operettas, as well as their deep content with strong educational power and social importance.

Appreciating the outstanding intellectuals of our nation – famous poets, cultural figures, famous scientists, promoting and protecting them in every possible way, the Great Leader attached special importance to

publicly celebrating anniversaries of those personalities and said: “World experience shows that celebrating anniversaries means, on the one hand, promoting and demonstrating the services of the anniversary celebrant to the people, country and the world once again, and on the other hand, the respect and esteem of the modern generation towards them” [7]. Emphasizing the progressive role played by such events in the cultural life of the society, in the education of the young generation, in preserving and protecting the rich traditions and national moral values of the people, Heydar Aliyev was also the direct organizer and initiator of the celebrations. The anniversaries of the classics of our music Uzeyir Hajibeyli, Muslim Magomayev, Bulbul, outstanding Azerbaijani composers Gara Garayev, Arif Malikov, Tofig Guliyev, Agshin Alizadeh, our prominent musicians Gurban Pirimov, Rashid Behbudov, Vagif Mustafazade, etc., which have become cultural holidays, serve as an example of this. H. Aliyev participated personally in all these solemn gatherings and gave speeches, exhibited his deep musical knowledge, attracted the attention of the listeners with his views expressing his interest and love for the life and work of the celebrated person. The Great Leader did not limit his interventions to simply listing facts and events but paid special attention to deeper issues within each topic. H. Aliyev gave speeches on U. Hajibeyli and M. Magomayev’s personalities and musical works on the evenings dedicated to their 110th anniversaries. “Every day of Uzeyir Hajibeyov’s life is precious for us. Every work, every sheet of music written by Uzeyir Hajibeyov is precious for us. Uzeyir Hajibeyov’s socio-political activity is valuable for us from the beginning to the end. Because all of them served the revival of the Azerbaijani people, the development of our culture, and the self-recognition of our people... These merits are invaluable” [9]. Not only the musical genius of the great composer was mentioned in the Great Leader’s speech, but also other areas of his social activity – enlightenment, political activity, even everyday life events, and the great personality of the musician was comprehensively revealed. The characteristic features of Heydar Aliyev’s evaluation of creative personality are also reflected in his following conclusion. “U. Hajibeyli was one of the great personalities of our nation with his extraordinary innate talent, great sacrifice, excellent education, intellect, patriotism, social and political activity, he was a prominent figure representing Azerbaijan, standing in the front row of world luminaries” [7] – by saying this, H. Aliyev introduced U. Hajibeyli

as the founder of the Azerbaijan professional composition school, music theorist, public figure, educator, playwright, writer, thus introducing comprehensive portrait of the composer.

The Great Leader also voiced valuable opinions about the establishment of a professional composition school in Azerbaijan and its traditions. He presented U. Hajibeyli's historical role in one of his speeches as following: "Azerbaijani music, especially professional music has a long history. The music school created by Uzeyir Hajibeyov in Azerbaijan was such a school, after which our people endowed the world with many outstanding composers, musicians and cultural figures" [7]. Indeed, the names of prominent representatives of the Azerbaijani composition school founded by Uzeyir Hajibeyli, such as G. Garayev, F. Amirov, J. Hajiyev, S. Hajibeyov, A. Malikov, A. Alizadeh and others have crossed the borders of their homeland and gained rightful place in various countries. This moment of our musical history did not escape H. Aliyev's attention, it made him happy and proud. Every new work, premiere, creative night, trip abroad of our composers was in the center of the Great Leader's attention. H. Aliyev always supported the colorful activities of our musical figures, called upon them to work towards cultural development of the nation with greater energy and strength, and showed that the traditions and rich heritage of our musical classics can help them in this way: "We must develop professional music in Azerbaijan. There is a great reason for this. As I said, the legacy of our great composers, musicians and performers is a great foundation" [5].

As a political figure, as a citizen, H. Aliyev saw the future of Azerbaijan in the education of the youth, and strived to create all conditions for the bringing up of a new creative generation. It is no coincidence that he was one of the main initiators of various concerts and competitions of young talents, performers, musicians and state-level events dedicated to their works. Although the country was in a difficult economic and political situation, and he had more urgent tasks awaiting him, he participated in each of these events, was interested in the creativity of young people, and spoke with them, sharing his impressions and ideas.

His speeches in front of the laureates and participants of the First International Music Festival held in Ashgabat during the meeting held at the Baku Music Academy on April 8, 1995, at the presentation concert of young talents at the Song Theater named after R. Behbudov on May 10,

1996, at the holiday concerts dedicated to the International Children's Day at the Azerbaijan Academic Opera and Ballet Theater on June 1, 1996-1997 were imbued with a sense of pride and joy for the young talents of his people: "It is very gratifying that Azerbaijan's art and music, which have a long history, bring up new talents every year. This shows the richness of culture and art of our people" [4]. H. Aliyev listened very carefully to the performance of young talents at all concerts, talked with them and gave them valuable recommendations to develop their art and work. However, he wisely acknowledged the fact that young talents should be protected by the state, they should be given special care and help: "It is necessary to show talent to the society, to the people, to help them develop their talent, to pave the way for the talent... Talents – children, young people should also know that the President of Azerbaijan will personally take care of all their concerns" [13] – said Heydar Aliyev, and kept his word while signing on June 22, 1996, a Decree entitled "State care for young talents in Azerbaijan" on the establishment of a special scholarship for the gifted youth of Azerbaijan listed in the "Golden Book", the "Young Talents Fund".

Music is the most powerful and at the same time the most delicate and lovely form of art that creates communication between people, the musical language is a universal language. People belonging to different nations and speaking different languages have the opportunity to listen, understand and analyze any piece of music in their own language. Because the word spoken in the language of music, the expressed idea, meaning, and mood will be understood by a person who has feelings, it will create a spiritual bridge between people of different languages. H. Aliyev also talked about such a bridge and means of communication in his speeches: "Nothing unites people as much as song, music, art and culture. No means can play the role as art, culture, especially song, music..." [1].

H. Aliyev considered efforts of the Azerbaijani people to establish friendly relations with other nations and strengthen friendship ties as one of the most important issues in domestic and foreign policy. And he attached great importance to holding cultural days of different states and peoples in Azerbaijan in ways of solving the problem. He participated personally in many of such events, had conversations with participants of the culture days, and always met with performers after the event. Heydar Aliyev attached great political importance to these events, explained the important role of music in

public life and said that despite all the difficulties, “Art brings us closer, art unites us, art makes us friends” [10].

The Great Leader considered tours of cultural figures to be important in this regard. It is no coincidence that the initiative of celebrating the 70th anniversary of the world-famous musician M. Rostropovich in Baku belonged to him. When H. Aliyev invited Maestro to Azerbaijan on the anniversary days of the cellist in Paris, his goal was not solely political. In order to further enrich cultural life of Azerbaijani people, he made it possible for them to listen to a musician with a rare talent, in his own words, the “Rostropovich phenomenon”, and communicate with him.

A lot has been said about H. Aliyev’s phenomenal memory, erudition, multifaceted interests. Many remember the Great Leader’s memorable speech after the concert dedicated to famous composer Arif Malikov at the Art Museum in Baku. Besides deep and comprehensive analysis of the concert program, the audience also went on a detailed tour of Azerbaijan’s musical history. It must be said that very few musicologists sitting in the hall could compete with the Head of State that day.

H. Aliyev said about himself: “I am a very sensitive person to poetry and song” [7]. It was impossible not to observe the colorful feelings on his face when watching the dance from the opera “Shah Ismail” at the concert given by our art masters on the occasion of 110th anniversary of M. Magomayev, when listening to grandson Muslim Magomayev’s song “Azerbaijan” and Tofiq Guliyev’s song “Sene de galmaz” (“Your Beauty Won’t Last”). H. Aliyev admitted this: “I love his (T. Guliyev – U.T.) song “Sene de galmaz” very much. You know, there are songs that stand out from all others. There are many Tofiq Guliyev’s songs, but “Sene de galmaz” is the top of them” [8].

The richness of the Great Leader’s ideas about music allows to make certain concrete opinions about many theoretical, aesthetic principles and problems of this important field of art. First of all, he talked about music in the context of historical development. He did not separate music of any nation from its roots and traditions. Based on this concept, each piece of music, new achievements of music were analyzed relative to its past and traditions. Let’s take a look at the following quote: “No matter how hard our country lives, our people have never forgotten their spirituality, culture, music, song and dance. Our culture, art, music and songs have kept our people alive in the spirit of faith in the future even in the most difficult

times and even today” [11]. So, the music of any nation is associated with its past and history for centuries; it contains the joy and sorrow of the people. Naturally, such a force becomes the moral support of the nation in difficult times.

History and modernity in the Great leader’s theoretical concept are presented as categories that complement each other and interact with each other. As can be seen from the examples above, he approached history, music history, and the classics of our music with modern view. H. Aliyev’s views on history were not explained separately in terms of nationality. He showed that U. Hajibeyli’s music is nourished by national musical roots, which ensures its longevity.

Our musicians, who saw and felt Heydar Aliyev’s endless interest and passion for music, the important work he did in this field, his protection and care, always expressed their gratitude to him and contributed to the development of Azerbaijani musical culture. Our late composer Arif Malikov said at one of M. Rostropovich’s anniversary events that he dedicated his next symphony to the President, which he wrote under the impressions he got from Saudi Arabia [2]. The famous composer Jovdat Hajiyev said about his 8th symphony “Onu Zaman sechib” (“Time chose him”), which he dedicated to the President: “History has put H. Aliyev behind the helm of our state at the most fateful time for the people of Azerbaijan since 1969, who has done his best for the prosperity of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the development of its culture and economy. And we, as people of art believe that the President, who has undertaken this huge task at such a difficult time, will successfully fulfill it for the sake of the statehood of Azerbaijan and the well-being of the people. I also tried to convey all my thoughts and emotions in the language of music in my 8th symphony” [3].

Conclusion. National leader Heydar Aliyev’s profound ideas explaining position, essence and tasks of culture in public life and the important work he did with a view to further developing and promoting Azerbaijani culture inspire musicians, as well as all cultural figures to search for new inspiration, to create. Today, our composers express their feelings to the National Leader in their works of various styles, and our scholars study his intense activities aimed at the development of Azerbaijani culture, valuable ideas and opinions in their research.

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Ülkər Talıbzadə (Azərbaycan)

ÜMUMMİLLİ LİDER HEYDƏR ƏLİYEV VƏ AZƏRBAYCAN MUSIQİ MƏDƏNİYYƏTİ

Məqalədə Azərbaycanın ümummilli lideri Heydər Əliyevin Azərbaycan musiqi mədəniyyəti, görkəmli incəsənət xadimləri ilə bağlı dərin fikirləri, həyata keçirdiyi möhtəşəm dövlət layihələri öz əksini tapmışdır. Parlaq fitri istedadada malik olan görkəmli dövlət xadimi üçün ictimai həyatın müxtəlif sahələri arsında sərhəd yox idi. O toxunduğu hər bir problemi mahir mütəxəssis kimi təqdim etmiş, həmin sahədə yüksək erudisiya, dərin məlumat, zəngin həyat təcrübəsinə malik olduğunu sübut etmişdi.

H.Əliyev tarixdə şəxsiyyətin rolu probleminə xüsusi önəm vermiş, müxtəlif musiqi xadimlərini yüksək qiymətləndirərək, dəyərli fikirlər söyləmişdir. Ulu öndərin musiqiyə dair zəngin fikirlərində, müxtəlif çıxış və məruzələrində formalaşan nəzəri konsepsiyasında tarixilik və müasirlik, ənənələr və tarixi inkişaf bir-birini tamamlayan, qarşılıqlı əlaqədə olan kateqoriyalar kimi təqdim edilmişdir.

Açar sözlər: Heydər Əliyev, musiqi mədəniyyəti, bəstəkarlar, musiqi xadimləri, milli ənənələr.

Улькяр Талыбзаде (Азербайджан)

ОБЩЕНАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ЛИДЕР ГЕЙДАР АЛИЕВ И МУЗЫКАЛЬНАЯ КУЛЬТУРА АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА

В статье отображены великие государственные и культурные проекты общенационального лидера Азербайджана Гейдара Алиева, а также его глубокие мысли о выдающихся артистах и музыкальной культуре Азербайджана. Для выдающегося государственного деятеля с блестящим врожденным талантом не было границ между различными областями общественной жизни. Каждую затронутую проблему он излагал как опытный специалист, доказывая, что обладает высокой эрудицией, глубокими знаниями и богатым жизненным опытом в этой области.

Г.Алиев придавал особое значение роли личности в истории, высоко ценил различных музыкальных деятелей и высказывал ценные мнения. В теоретической концепции, сформированной в речах и докладах великого общенационального лидера, а также в его богатых представлениях о музыке, переплелись взаимодополняющие и взаимосвязанные категории об истории и современности, традициях и историческом развитии музыкальной культуры Азербайджана.

Ключевые слова: Гейдар Алиев, музыкальная культура, композиторы, музыкальные деятели, национальные традиции.